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CULTURAL AND PSYCHOSOCIAL DIMENSIONS OF SOCIAL INTEGRATION AMONG SYRIAN MUSLIM MIGRANTS: EVIDENCE FROM A SCALE DEVELOPMENT STUDY

A. Muhammet Banazılı¹, Aysel Akbeniz²

¹Assoc. Prof. Dr., Tarsus University, Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, Department of Political Science and Public Administration. ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5088-9587>

²Assoc. Prof. Dr., Tarsus University, Faculty of Health Sciences, Department of Nursing.
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5163-5258>

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Corresponding Author: Aysel Akbeniz
(aysel_akbeniz@hotmail.com)

ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine the cultural and psychosocial dimensions of social integration among Syrian Muslim migrants and to develop a valid and reliable measurement tool to assess their integration intentions within the host society. A quantitative research design was employed. The study was conducted with 125 Syrian Muslim migrants residing in neighborhoods with a high concentration of migrant populations. An initial pool of 20 items was generated based on a comprehensive literature review and expert evaluations. Content validity was assessed using the Content Validity Ratio (CVR). Construct validity was examined through exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). Reliability analyses included Cronbach's alpha coefficient, item-total correlations, and test-retest reliability. The analyses revealed a unidimensional structure consisting of five items, explaining 60.932% of the total variance, with factor loadings ranging from 0.641 to 0.860. The scale demonstrated strong internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha = 0.832) and satisfactory test-retest reliability. The findings indicate that integration intentions are primarily shaped by interpersonal relationships, cultural meanings, and subjective experiences of belonging within the host society. This study conceptualizes social integration as a culturally embedded and psychosocial process rather than solely a structural outcome. By emphasizing everyday social interactions, symbolic meanings, and relational experiences, the developed scale provides a culturally sensitive and non-stigmatizing tool for assessing integration intentions. The findings offer a framework for interdisciplinary research and may inform policies aimed at fostering inclusive and socially cohesive environments.

KEYWORDS: Social Integration, Syrian Muslim Migrants, Psychosocial Integration, Cultural Integration, Migration and Well-Being.

1. INTRODUCTION

Migration in the contemporary world has become one of the most significant social phenomena shaped by globalization, transforming not only economic and political systems but also cultural structures, identities, and social relations. Advances in information and communication technologies have accelerated human mobility and intensified interactions between culturally diverse populations. As a result, migration should be understood not merely as a demographic or economic process, but as a deeply cultural phenomenon involving the reconfiguration of meanings, identities, and social boundaries (Adıgüzel, 2019).

In this context, the concept of social integration has gained increasing importance within migration studies. Social integration extends beyond migrants' access to structural opportunities such as employment, education, and healthcare, and encompasses processes of belonging, recognition, and participation within the host society. Contemporary approaches emphasize that integration is a multidimensional and dynamic phenomenon shaped by legal-political, socio-economic, and cultural-religious dimensions (Penninx & Garcés-Mascareñas, 2016). Among these, the cultural dimension is particularly central, as it reflects how migrants are positioned within symbolic systems of meaning, everyday practices, and social relations.

From a cultural perspective, integration is closely linked to the concept of belonging, which reflects individuals' emotional attachment, social positioning, and recognition within a community (Yuval-Davis, 2006). Belonging is not only an individual feeling but also a socially constructed condition shaped by power relations, cultural norms, and collective identities. In this sense, integration involves continuous negotiation between migrants and host societies, in which identities are redefined and social boundaries are constructed and contested. These boundaries determine who is included, excluded, or positioned as the "other" within the social order (Wimmer, 2008).

Moreover, recent critical perspectives argue that integration should not be conceptualized as a linear or unidirectional process in which migrants are expected to adapt to a fixed social structure. Instead, integration is a relational and context-dependent process shaped by broader social, political, and epistemological dynamics (Schinkel, 2018). This perspective highlights that integration is not only about adaptation, but also about recognition, interaction, and the negotiation of difference within

culturally diverse societies.

Within this framework, integration emerges as a culturally embedded and psychosocial process shaped by everyday interactions, social networks, and shared meanings (Ager & Strang, 2008; Friese, 2010). Feelings of belonging, acceptance, and social connectedness become key indicators of integration, reflecting migrants' subjective experiences within the host society. Therefore, understanding integration requires examining not only structural conditions but also migrants' perceptions, intentions, and lived experiences.

The case of Syrian migrants in Türkiye provides a particularly important context for examining these dynamics. Following the political unrest that began in Syria in 2011, Türkiye became the primary destination for one of the largest forced migration movements of the 21st century. While the country adopted an "open-door" policy, the resulting increase in cultural diversity has brought significant challenges related to social cohesion, coexistence, and mutual acceptance (Çatak, 2020; İçduygu et al., 2014). Syrians in Türkiye are legally classified under temporary protection status rather than as refugees, which further complicates their social positioning and integration processes (Özel, 2020; Şimşek, 2018).

Despite the growing body of literature on migration and social cohesion, existing research has largely focused on the perceptions and attitudes of host societies toward migrants, often overlooking migrants' own perspectives (Balci, 2022; Erdoğan, 2018; Zihnioğlu & Dalkıran, 2022). However, integration cannot be fully understood without considering how migrants themselves interpret their position within the host society and how they construct their sense of belonging and social connectedness.

In addition, religious identity may play a significant role in shaping integration processes, particularly in contexts where migrants and host communities share similar cultural or religious backgrounds. For Syrian Muslim migrants in Türkiye, shared religious and cultural elements may function as symbolic bridges that facilitate social interaction and foster a sense of familiarity and belonging. At the same time, integration remains a complex and negotiated process influenced by broader dynamics of inclusion, exclusion, and cultural recognition (Yuval-Davis, 2006).

Accordingly, this study conceptualizes social integration primarily as a cultural and psychosocial phenomenon rather than solely as a structural or legal outcome. Psychosocial integration is understood through migrants' subjective experiences

of belonging, social connectedness, and everyday interpersonal relationships within the host society. In this framework, integration intentions are considered an important indicator reflecting migrants' orientation toward the host society and their willingness to engage in social and cultural interaction.

Despite the importance of this perspective, there remains a limited number of measurement tools that capture migrants' integration intentions within a culturally grounded and psychosocial framework. Therefore, the present study aims to contribute to the literature by examining the cultural and psychosocial dimensions of social integration among Syrian Muslim migrants and by developing a valid and reliable measurement tool to assess their integration intentions. While the study employs a quantitative scale development approach, its primary contribution lies in providing a culturally informed understanding of integration as a lived and relational experience shaped by identity, meaning, and social interaction.

The purpose of this study is to examine the cultural and psychosocial dimensions of social integration among Syrian Muslim migrants and to develop a measurement tool, the Social Integration Intentions Scale (SIIS), to assess their integration intentions within the host society. Rather than conceptualizing integration solely as a structural or legal outcome, this study approaches it as a culturally embedded and relational process shaped by belonging, social connectedness, and everyday interactions.

2. METHOD

To achieve this aim, a quantitative methodological design was employed. Quantitative research enables the systematic and objective examination of social phenomena through numerical data, allowing for the identification and analysis of patterns, relationships, and underlying structures (Garip, 2023). In the context of this study, quantitative methods were used not only to measure integration intentions but also to provide empirical insight into the psychosocial and cultural aspects of integration as experienced by migrants.

Accordingly, the phenomenon of social integration was examined in relation to migration, with particular attention to migrants' subjective orientations toward the host society. The SIIS was developed as a tool to capture these orientations, reflecting migrants' feelings of belonging, social affiliation, and willingness to engage in cultural and social interaction. While the study involves scale

development and psychometric testing, its broader objective is to contribute to the cultural understanding of integration by linking measurable indicators with migrants' lived experiences.

2.1. Population and Sample

The study sample was formed using a convenience sampling method among Syrian Muslim migrants residing in neighborhoods with a high concentration of the target population. This approach was preferred to facilitate access to participants and to capture the lived experiences of migrants within their everyday social environments.

Inclusion Criteria

- Currently holding Syrian citizenship.
- Being 18 years of age or older.
- Residing in one of the specified neighborhoods.
- Having a functional level of spoken Turkish.
- Exclusion Criteria
- Having acquired Turkish citizenship.
- Experiencing communication difficulties.
- Having a self-reported severe psychiatric condition that could impair participation.

Withdrawal Criteria

- Expressing a wish to withdraw from the study at any stage.

2.2. Scale Development Procedure

The development of the Social Integration Intentions Scale (SIIS) followed a systematic multi-step procedure. First, a review of the relevant literature on migration, social integration, belonging, and psychosocial adaptation was conducted, and existing measurement tools were examined. Based on the conceptual framework derived from the literature, an initial item pool was generated. The items were written to reflect migrants' subjective orientations toward belonging, social connectedness, and cultural interaction within the host society.

Particular attention was paid to the use of culturally sensitive, non-stigmatizing, and inclusive language during item construction. To avoid exclusionary wording and to improve the broader applicability of the scale, the term "host society" was preferred instead of referring to a specific national or ethnic group.

For content validity, the preliminary item pool was submitted to a panel of experts from public administration and political science, psychiatric nursing, and language studies. The experts were asked to evaluate the relevance, clarity, and comprehensibility of each item. Content validity was

assessed using the Davis technique, and the Content Validity Ratio (CVR) was calculated for each item to determine whether the items adequately represented the intended construct.

Following the expert review, a pilot study was conducted with 30 individuals who had characteristics similar to those of the target sample but were not included in the main study. The purpose of the pilot application was to evaluate the clarity, comprehensibility, and linguistic appropriateness of the items before the main data collection process.

2.3. Data Collection Instruments

The data for this study were collected using a Personal Information Form and the SIIS.

Personal Information Form The Personal Information Form consisted of five items designed to collect demographic information from the Syrian Muslim migrant participants.

Scale of Social Integration Intentions (SIIS) The Social Integration Intentions Scale (SIIS) was developed to assess migrants' integration intentions as a psychosocial and culturally embedded construct. The scale aims to capture individuals' subjective experiences of belonging, social connectedness, and engagement in everyday interpersonal interactions within the host society.

The SIIS consists of five items rated on a five-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree). The total score ranges from 5 to 25, with higher scores indicating stronger intentions toward social integration.

The items were formulated using culturally sensitive and non-stigmatizing language. To enhance the generalizability of the scale and to avoid exclusionary or potentially biased wording, the term "host society" was consistently used instead of referring to a specific national or ethnic group. In the context of this study, the term "host society" refers to Türkiye, where the data were collected.

Unlike purely structural indicators of integration, the SIIS focuses on psychosocial dimensions, including feelings of belonging, perceived social acceptance, and willingness to engage in everyday social interactions. In this respect, the scale reflects migrants' orientations toward integration as a lived and relational process shaped by cultural meanings and social experiences.

The scale does not include reverse-coded items or subdimensions. The Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient for the scale was found to be 0.832, indicating high internal consistency. The final version of the scale is presented in the Appendix.

2.4. Data Collection Process

Data were collected between May 1 and July 1, 2025, following ethical approval. The data collection process was conducted by the researcher in neighborhoods with a high concentration of Syrian Muslim migrants. Participants were informed about the purpose of the study, and confidentiality and voluntariness were emphasized. Each data collection session lasted approximately 10-15 minutes. The questionnaires were administered face-to-face by the researcher. Special attention was given to creating a safe and respectful environment that allowed participants to express their perspectives on social interaction, belonging, and integration without hesitation.

2.5. Data Analysis

The analysis process was designed to ensure both the psychometric robustness of the scale and its conceptual relevance to the cultural and psychosocial dimensions of integration.

Content validity was assessed through expert evaluation using the Davis technique to calculate the Content Validity Ratio (CVR). The validation process was carried out in successive stages, including content validity assessment, pilot testing, construct validity analysis, and reliability testing. Construct validity was examined using Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). In the EFA process, factor loadings of 0.40 or higher and eigenvalues greater than 1 were considered as the main criteria for factor retention. These analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics 22 and IBM SPSS Amos 24.

Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation) and Pearson correlation coefficients were used to examine relationships between variables. For EFA, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity were applied, followed by Principal Component Analysis. For CFA, model fit was evaluated using indices including χ^2/df , GFI, AGFI, CFI, and RMSEA. Reliability analyses included Cronbach's alpha coefficient, item-total correlations, independent samples t-test, and test-retest analysis. These procedures ensured that the scale not only demonstrated statistical consistency but also provided a reliable framework for understanding migrants' integration intentions as a measurable reflection of their cultural and psychosocial experiences.

2.6. Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics

Committee of Tarsus University for Social and Human Sciences Research (Approval Date: April 30, 2025; Protocol Number: 2025/64). Participants were informed about the purpose of the study, and their voluntary participation was ensured. They were also informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences.

2.7. Limitations of the Study

This study was conducted in a single geographical context. Therefore, the findings are limited to the specific socio-cultural environment in which the data were collected and may not be generalizable to other contexts.

3. RESULTS

The findings are presented not only as statistical outcomes but also as indicators of migrants' psychosocial orientations toward belonging, social connectedness, and engagement in cultural interaction within the host society.

3.1. Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Participants

According to the results, 32.8% of the Syrian Muslim migrant participants were between the ages of 35 and 44, 58.4% were female, all participants (100%) were married, 28% had completed high school, and 64% were currently employed (Table 1).

3.2. Results Related to the Validity of the Scale

Content Validity Initially, a literature review was conducted, existing measurement instruments were examined, and a content analysis was performed. Subsequently, consultations were held with field experts, and the information obtained was transformed into items, resulting in an item pool of 20 items.

To ensure content validity—that is, to test whether the items in the pool adequately measure the intended construct—the item pool was presented to experts in public administration and political science (three experts), psychiatric nursing (three experts), and language (one expert). The experts were asked to evaluate whether the items were appropriate in terms of the scope and content of the construct to be measured, as well as their clarity and comprehensibility from a linguistic perspective. The Content Validity Ratio (CVR) was calculated for each item. The CVR values ranged between 0.42 and 1.00. According to Büyüköztürk (2017, p. 141), the minimum acceptable CVR value for 10 experts at a significance level of 0.05 is 0.62. Five items fell below this threshold (2, 4, 5, 8, and 15) and were therefore

removed from the scale. The CVR values for the remaining 15 items ranged from 0.65 to 1.00, indicating the experts' unanimous acceptance of these items for inclusion in the draft scale.

This 15-item draft scale was then piloted with a homogeneous group of 30 individuals similar to the target sample; however, these participants were not included in the main study. During the pilot, participants were asked questions such as "Are there any expressions you do not understand?" and "Were the questions clear?" to gather feedback. The items were ultimately deemed comprehensible.

Subsequent to the pilot study, the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) revealed that three items (1, 3, and 10) exhibited factor loadings below the threshold of 0.40. As noted by Tabachnick and Fidell (2013, p. 28), factor loadings below 0.40 suggest that these items do not demonstrate a statistically meaningful association with the underlying factor. Consequently, these items were excluded from the scale, and the research progressed to the field phase to perform comprehensive validity and reliability assessments of the refined instrument.

Construct Validity To assess the construct validity of the scale, the adequacy of the sample size was first evaluated using the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy, and the significance of the relationships among variables was examined through Bartlett's Test of Sphericity prior to conducting Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA). For the 12-item form of the scale, the KMO value was found to be 0.781, indicating that the sample was adequate for factor analysis. Additionally, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity yielded statistically significant results ($\chi^2 = 641.772$, $df = 28$, $p < .001$), confirming the suitability of the data for factor analysis (Hair et al., 2019, pp. 356-360). During the EFA process, the Varimax rotation method was employed to preserve the orthogonal structure of the factors (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013, p. 638).

Based on the results obtained, to reduce cross-dimensional variance and increase the total explained variance, seven items with factor loadings below 0.40 (7, 11, 12, 14, 17, 18, and 19) were removed from the analysis, and the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was completed. The factor loadings for the remaining items ranged between 0.641 and 0.860 (Table 2). These findings suggest that social integration intentions are closely associated with everyday social relationships and feelings of cultural proximity within the host society.

The analysis yielded a Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy of 0.813 and a statistically significant Bartlett's Test of Sphericity (χ^2

= 242.52, $df = 10$, $p < .001$). According to the EFA results, only one factor with an eigenvalue greater than 1 was identified, accounting for 60.932% of the total variance. The validity of the item-factor structure obtained through EFA was further examined via Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to assess the overall model fit (Worthington & Whittaker, 2006, p. 822).

Within the scope of CFA, the fit indices for the unidimensional structure of the scale were evaluated. As a result of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), it was determined that the unidimensional structure of the developed scale was valid and that no structural modifications to the model were necessary. However, to improve model fit indices, suggested error covariances were taken into account, and a modification was made between item 2 and item 4. Following this adjustment, an improvement in the model fit indices was observed. The path diagram of the confirmed model, along with the factor loadings for each item, is presented in Figure 1.

The observed values and model fit indices for the scale are presented in detail in Table 3. All fit indices obtained indicate that the model demonstrates an excellent level of fit (Büyüköztürk, 2017, p. 231). The strong model fit indicates that the identified structure meaningfully reflects migrants' psychosocial orientations toward belonging and social interaction.

3.3. Results Related to the Reliability of the Scale

Item Analysis and Internal Consistency Results of the Scale To assess the reliability of the scale, the total Cronbach's alpha coefficient and item-total correlation values were examined based on the unidimensional structure obtained from the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) (Tavşancıl, 2014, pp. 50-55). Additionally, to determine the effect of each item on the overall reliability of the scale, the Cronbach's alpha coefficients if each item was deleted were calculated, and these results are presented in Table 4. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the unidimensional scale was found to be 0.832.

In another phase of the study, to assess the temporal stability of the scale, a retest was administered two weeks later to the last 50 migrant participants who completed the initial survey. The relationship between scores from the first and second administrations was analyzed using Pearson's correlation coefficient, yielding a test-retest reliability coefficient of $r = 0.731$ ($p < .001$). This result indicates that the scale produces consistent results over time

and demonstrates high test-retest reliability (Karasar, 2005, p. 95).

Overall, the findings indicate that social integration intentions among Syrian Muslim migrants are primarily shaped by relational and cultural factors rather than solely structural conditions. The prominence of items related to social interaction, emotional attachment, and cultural engagement highlights the importance of belonging and everyday interpersonal connections in the integration process.

4. DISCUSSION

In this study, a scale measuring the intentions of Syrian Muslim migrants to integrate into the host society was developed, and it was determined that the scale is a valid and reliable measurement tool. The results obtained are discussed in light of the relevant literature. From a religion and health perspective, social integration intentions may be closely linked to psychosocial well-being, as feelings of acceptance, belonging, and social connectedness are known to influence both mental health and adaptive functioning among migrant populations.

To ensure content validity, the initial item pool was presented to experts in relevant fields, and the Content Validity Ratio (CVR) was calculated for each item. According to the literature, at a significance level of 0.05 with 10 experts, the CVR threshold should not be below 0.62 (Büyüköztürk, 2017, p. 141). The analysis revealed that five items had CVR values below 0.62 and were therefore removed from the scale. The CVR values of the remaining 15 items ranged from 0.65 to 1.00, indicating unanimous acceptance of these items by the experts for inclusion in the draft scale.

The 15-item draft version of the scale was piloted with a group of 30 individuals exhibiting characteristics similar to those of the sample population. Pilot testing is a crucial step to assess the comprehensibility of the scale, identify potential linguistic or phrasing issues, and prepare for validity and reliability analyses (De Vellis, 2016, p. 24). However, the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) conducted following the pilot revealed that three items (1, 3, and 10) had factor loadings below 0.40. Factor loadings below this threshold indicate that these items are not significantly associated with the underlying factor (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013, p. 28). These items were subsequently removed to ensure the scale's content validity.

Prior to conducting the EFA to determine construct validity, the adequacy of the sample size was evaluated using the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO)

test, and the significance of the correlations among variables was assessed via Bartlett's Test of Sphericity. A KMO value above 0.60 and a statistically significant Bartlett's test indicate that the data are suitable for factor analysis (Field, 2018, pp. 1012-1013). In this study, the KMO measure of sampling adequacy was found to be 0.813, and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was significant ($\chi^2 = 242.52$, $df = 10$, $p < .001$), confirming the suitability of the data for EFA.

Factor analysis is a multivariate statistical technique used to reduce a large number of interrelated variables into a smaller set of independent factors that reflect their underlying structure. According to the literature, for a factor structure to be considered valid, factor loadings should be at least 0.40, and the total explained variance should account for at least 50% of the overall variance (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019, pp. 437-453).

Based on the analysis results, to increase the explained variance and reduce variance among dimensions, seven items with factor loadings below 0.40 (7, 11, 12, 14, 17, 18, and 19) were removed, and the EFA was completed. The final factor loadings for the remaining items ranged from 0.641 to 0.860. The analysis identified a single factor with an eigenvalue greater than 1, explaining 60.932% of the total variance. These results demonstrate that the scale's EFA results are consistent with the literature and appropriate for Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA).

The fit indices and modification values for the unidimensional model obtained from the EFA were further examined using CFA. Various fit indices—including χ^2 , χ^2/df , GFI, AGFI, RMSEA, RMR, NFI, and CFI—are commonly employed to assess how well the model fits the data (Kline, 2016, pp. 268-276). The fit indices obtained in this study were as follows: $\chi^2/df = 2.297$, RMSEA = 0.000, GFI = 0.993, CFI = 1.000, NFI = 0.991, AGFI = 0.974, and RMR = 0.012. These values indicate an excellent model fit according to established criteria (Hooper et al., 2008, p. 55).

In the reliability assessment of Likert-type scales, Cronbach's alpha coefficient, calculated based on total scores, is widely used (Tavşancıl, 2014, p. 80). The scale's unidimensional Cronbach's alpha was calculated as 0.832. According to accepted guidelines for interpreting Cronbach's alpha, values between 0.80 and 1.00 indicate "high reliability" (De Vellis, 2016, pp. 95-96). The calculated alpha coefficient thus demonstrates a high level of reliability for the scale. Furthermore, the test-retest correlation coefficient was found to be $r = 0.731$ ($p < .001$). This result indicates high test-retest reliability and confirms that

the scale produces stable and consistent measurements over time (Field, 2013, p. 122). These results support the consistency of the scale in capturing integration intentions as a stable psychosocial construct.

5. CONCLUSION

This study examined the cultural and psychosocial dimensions of social integration among Syrian Muslim migrants and provided empirical insights into how integration is experienced as a relational and meaning-based process. The findings demonstrate that social integration is not limited to structural or institutional inclusion but is deeply embedded in everyday social interactions, emotional attachment, and perceptions of belonging within the host society.

The results highlight that migrants' integration intentions are primarily shaped by interpersonal relationships, cultural proximity, and opportunities for social engagement. In this sense, integration emerges as a lived experience constructed through daily encounters, shared practices, and symbolic connections rather than solely through formal mechanisms. These findings underscore the importance of considering integration as a culturally situated and psychosocial phenomenon.

Another important implication of the study is the role of shared cultural and religious elements in facilitating integration processes. For Syrian Muslim migrants, common cultural references and religious identity may function as symbolic bridges that support social interaction and contribute to a sense of familiarity and belonging. However, integration remains a complex and dynamic process influenced by broader societal conditions, including acceptance, exclusion, and opportunities for meaningful participation.

From a methodological perspective, this study developed a valid and reliable instrument to assess integration intentions. Nevertheless, beyond its measurement contribution, the study advances the literature by framing integration as a culturally embedded and relational construct that reflects migrants' subjective experiences and orientations toward the host society.

Overall, the findings suggest that policies and practices aimed at promoting integration should move beyond purely structural approaches and prioritize the enhancement of social interaction, mutual recognition, and inclusive cultural environments. Supporting opportunities for everyday contact and fostering a sense of belonging may play a crucial role in strengthening integration

processes.

While the study provides valuable insights, it is limited to a specific geographical context. Future research may extend this framework to different

cultural settings and migrant groups to further explore the multidimensional and context-dependent nature of social integration.

Author Contributions: AMB contributed to the conceptualization, methodology, investigation, data curation, formal analysis, and writing of the original draft. AA contributed to supervision, validation, writing (review and editing), project administration, and resources. All authors contributed to the interpretation of the data, critically revised the manuscript for important intellectual content, and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Competing interests: The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethical approval: This study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics Committee of Tarsus University, Türkiye, on April 30, 2025 (Approval No.: 2025/64).

Informed consent: A written informed consent form was provided to the participants by the researchers. The consent form was embedded in the questionnaire, and responses indicating participants' consent were collected between May and July 2025. The purpose of the study was clearly explained to the participants, and they were informed that they could withdraw from the study at any time if they did not wish to participate in the questionnaire.

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Table 1: Sociodemographic Characteristics of Syrian Muslim Migrants (n = 125).

Sociodemographic Characteristics	N	%
Age		
18-24	24	19.2
25-34	32	25.6
35-44	41	32.8
45-54	15	12
55 and over	13	10.4
Gender		
Male	52	41.6
Female	73	58.4
Married Status		
Married	125	100
Education Status		
Literate	31	24.8
Primary School	26	20.8
Middle School	26	20.8
High School	35	28
University	7	5.6
Working Status		
Employed	80	64
Unemployed	45	36

Table 2: Distribution of Factor Loadings.

Original Item Number	Scale Items	Factor Loadings
S6	I feel happy living in the host country.	.641
S9	I feel a sense of belonging with people in the host society.	.839
S13	Learning about the host country's culture makes me feel positive.	.801
S16	I engage in friendly social interactions with people in the host society.	.741
S20	I feel comfortable having neighbors from the host community.	.860

Figure 1: Path Diagram of Factor Loadings.

Table 3: Model Fit Statistics and Observed Estimates.

Model	N	χ^2	sd	χ^2/ sd	CFI	GFI	NFI	AGFI	RMR	RMSEA
Single-Factor Structure	125	2.297	4	.574	1.000	.993	.991	.974	.012	.000
Model Fit Indices				< 3	> .90	> .90	> .90	> .85	< .05	< .05

Table 4: Analysis of the Scale Items.

Scale Items	Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
S6	.486	.840
S9	.705	.779
S13	.663	.791
S16	.588	.813
S20	.743	.765

Appendix 1: Social Integration Intentions Scale (SIIS).

ITEMS	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1. I feel happy living in the host country.					
2. I feel a sense of belonging with people in the host society.					
3. Learning about the host country's culture makes me feel positive.					
4. I engage in friendly social interactions with people in the host society.					
5. I feel comfortable having neighbors from the host community.					

The SIIS consists of five items rated on a five-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree). The total score ranges from 5 to 25, with higher scores indicating stronger intentions toward social integration.